

MAtchUP

D2.12: New citizens' engagement strategies in Valencia

WP 2, T 2.7.2

Date of document

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Authors: Barbara Branchini, Francisco Azorín, Beatriz Vallina (KVEL), Veronica Meneghello (ICE), M^a José Perales (LNV)

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Abbreviations and Acronyms

Acronym	Description
EC	European Commission
ToC	Table of Content
IAP2	International Association for Public Participation
ICT	Information and Communication Technologies
Dn.n	Deliverable and numbers
URL	Uniform Resource Locator
VLC	Valencia
WS	Workshop
WP	Work Package
Mnn	Month and number
CC	Communication Campaign
CE	Citizens' Engagement

0 Abstract

This report constitutes Deliverable “D2.12: *New citizens' engagement strategies in Valencia – 1st version*”, which is the main outcome of Task “T2.7.2: *Citizens' engagement and empowering*”. The 2nd and final versions of this report (i.e. D2.26 and D2.27, respectively) will be delivered in September 2019 (project month M24) and September 2020 (M36).

First of all, the conceptual framework used for the citizen engagement strategies in Valencia is described. Under this framework, we understand the citizen engagement as a process of institutional and citizens' transformation, entailing different levels of public participation with the final aim of empowering citizens through the involvement in the decision making and policies processes. The MAtchUP citizen engagement strategy is based on a four-steps process including: ecosystem analysis, diagnosis, action plan and communication, described in this report (**Chapter 2**).

The strategy is based, in fact, on the analysis of the existing infrastructure, processes and relevant stakeholders for the public participation at the city and district level (**Chapter 3**). The selection of suitable resources and key actors from civil society, business and industry, research and education allows to benefit from synergies and to avoid an overlapping of measures or citizens overburden. The action plan (**Chapter 5**) then builds on the existing resources and relevant actors and designs the participatory activities according to the level of participation entailed by the MAtchUP interventions in Valencia.

To this end, a thorough diagnosis, involving the WP2 partners in charge of the interventions was performed. Furthermore, experts' feedback on the public participation is included as recommendations with the purpose of fine-tuning the engagement action plan (**Chapter 4**).

The MAtchUP infrastructure for the citizen engagement (**Chapter 4**) as well as the communication measures (**Chapter 6**) are defined.

Additional channels and measures of public participation are planned to be added during the course of the project and will be included into the updated versions of this Deliverable (i.e. D2.26 and D2.27).

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose and target group

The purpose of this report “D2.12: New citizens' engagement strategies in Valencia – 1st version”, is to describe the citizen engagement strategy that will be deployed in the Valencia demonstration site (i.e. the district of Poblats Marítims) under the MAtchUP project. This strategy is the main outcome of Task “T2.7.2: Citizens' engagement and empowerment”. The 2nd and final versions of this report (i.e. D2.26 and D2.27, respectively) will be delivered in September 2019 (project month M24) and September 2020 (M36).

The MAtchUP citizen engagement strategy will be deployed following a four-steps process including ecosystem analysis, diagnosis, action plan and communication. The strategy is based, in fact, on the analysis of the existing infrastructure, processes and relevant stakeholders for the public participation at the city and district level. The selection of suitable resources and key actors from civil society, business and industry, research and education allows to benefit from synergies and to avoid an overlapping of measures or citizens overburden. The action plan then builds on the existing resources and relevant actors and designs the participatory activities according to the level of participation entailed by the MAtchUP interventions in Valencia. The MAtchUP infrastructure for the citizen engagement as well as the communication measures are defined.

1.2 Contribution of partners

The **TABLE 1** depicts the main contributions from participant partners in the development of this deliverable.

Participant short name	Contributions
KVEL	Task and deliverable responsible party. Table of Content (ToC), Chapter 1 (Introduction), Chapter 2 (MAtchUP citizens' engagement process, Chapter 3 (Ecosystem analysis), Chapter 4 (Diagnosis), Chapter 5 (Action Plan), Chapter 6 (Dissemination & Communication Plan), Annex
ICE	Input for ToC of Chapter 6
LNV	Input for Chapters 4 and 6

Table 1. Contribution of partners

1.3 Relation to other activities in the project

The **TABLE 2** depicts the main relationship of this deliverable to other activities (or deliverables) developed within the MAtchUP Project and that should be considered along with this document for further understanding of its contents.

Deliverable Number	Relation
D1.1	D1.1 defines the Citizen Engagement approach followed in MAtchUP.

Deliverable Number	Relation
D1.2	D1.2 describes the approach, methodology, infrastructures and processes for capacity building and citizen engagement activities followed in MAtchUP.
D1.7	The findings from this D2.12 and the developed Action Plan will be the basis for further discussions and strategy development related to citizen engagement in the Smart City Strategic Plan for Valencia.
D1.14	The findings from this D2.12 and the developed Action Plan will be an input for the Valencia Replication Plan.
D2.x	The strategy for public participation developed will accompany the whole MAtchUP actions implementation process at the Valencia demo-site.
D7.x	The strategy developed in Chapter 6 for publication, participation will go hand in hand with international projects to support the implementation processes of sustainable Action Plans of other cities.
D5.7	The social evaluation will facilitate the monitoring and assessment of the citizen engagement strategy and both D2.12 and D5.7 will provide an evidence-based ground for future experiences and public participation strategies.
D8.11	The strategy developed for public participation will go hand in hand with local and project-wide dissemination and communication activities.

Table 2. Relation to other activities in the project

2 MATCHUP Citizens' engagement process

We understand **citizen engagement** as a process of institutional and citizens' transformation. The participation of the quadruple helix of open innovation is therefore essential.

Figure 1. Quadruple helix of open innovation

The process of citizen engagement entails different **levels of public participation** (Inform, Involve, Consult, Collaborate and Empower), depending on the characteristics of the actions planned in a given programme, plan or project.

	DECREASING LEVEL OF PUBLIC IMPACT				
	INFORM	CONSULT	INVOLVE	COLLABORATE	EMPOWER
GOAL	To provide balanced and objective information in a timely manner.	To obtain feedback on analysis, issues, alternatives and decisions.	To work with the public to make sure that concerns and aspirations are considered and understood.	To partner with the public in each aspect of the decision-making.	To place final decision-making in the hands of the public.
PROMISE	"We will keep you informed"	"We will listen to and acknowledge your concerns."	"We will work with you to ensure your concerns and aspirations are directly reflected in the decisions made."	"We will look to you for advice and innovation and incorporate this in decisions as much as possible."	"We will implement what you decide."

Figure 2. Spectrum of Public Participation

Source: Vancouver Mayor's Engaged City Task Force. Final Report, 2014, based on the IAP2 Public Participation Spectrum.

Under the MAtchUP citizen engagement strategy, the level of participation required by the Lighthouse interventions is analysed, in order to determine the level of engagement actions required.

The **highest participation level** is the empowerment and it is reached through the involvement in the decision making and policies processes. A citizen engagement strategy has to cover three main dimensions in order to enable a real empowerment:

- Awareness about the action site
- Capacity building – at the individual and collective level
- Generation of a favourable environment allowing the development of an active and binding participation

These three dimensions will be covered under the four MAtchUP pillars: Energy, Mobility, ICT and Citizens.

Figure 3. MAtchUP Pillars

Along the Project several participatory activities are planned: under WP1 along the characterization and the strategic planning, under WP8 under the Communication and Dissemination activities, and, in the demo sites, along the citizens' engagement actions (WP2-4). The features of **participation, co-decision, social inclusion and synergies with existing initiatives** (for further details on these features, see D1.1, p. 16-17) shall nurture the MAtchUp processes, both at the city and the project level. The several participatory activities scheduled along the Project should be understood as a continuous process and the **synergies** among the citizens' engagement actions, and between them and the existing initiatives under the planning, demonstration and replication actions should be identified, put in value and strengthened.

In order to clarify the **common participatory environment**, the following figure (FIGURE 4) shows the citizens' engagement infrastructure and processes planned along the Project at different levels, allowing to conceptualize them as parts of one common framework.

Figure 4. MATCHUP Citizens' Engagement Strategies

The MAtchUP citizen engagement strategy will be deployed following a four-steps process, summarized in the following paragraphs and detailed in Chapters 3, 4 and 5, including:

1. Ecosystem analysis
2. Diagnosis
3. Action plan
4. Dissemination and communication

2.1 Ecosystem analysis

The initial phase of the Ecosystem Analysis includes gathering information on existing resources for the public participation in the city of Valencia both in terms of relevant infrastructure and strategies i. Existing and planned resources and strategies that are complementary to the MAtchUP strategy are identified, in order to establish synergies and not to overlap. The collaboration with private initiatives working in line with the MAtchUP goals is encouraged, promoted and disseminated. The ecosystem analysis and diagnosis proceeds in parallel to the analysis of the city plans and indicators (WP1, City Advanced Characterization, Step 1) and they are mutually nurtured.

2.2 Diagnosis

The Diagnosis phase allows defining the contextual basis for the Engagement Action Plan. To this end, as a first step the existing virtual and F2F infrastructures suitable for MAtchUP at the city and district level are selected, based on the Ecosystem analysis performed (Chapter 3), together with relevant key alliances. Besides, recommendations based on the input collected within the *WS1.-Diagnosis Launch Workshop*, held in Valencia the 3rd of July 2018 under the WP1 activities (see D1.1), allow the fine-tuning of the engagement action plan. The level of participation required by the Lighthouse interventions is then analysed, in order to determine the level of engagement actions required under the Action Plan. The virtual and face to face infrastructure that have to be created in order to implement the engagement strategy (together with the existing ones) are finally designed.

2.3 Action plan

An action plan designs the desired scenario that the actors want to reach as an answer to the characteristics analysed; therefore, the action plan designed for the Valencian citizen engagement strategy is based on the Ecosystem analysis and the Diagnosis. This has to be an action-oriented timeline, identifying key available resources and key responsibilities. At the current time, the action plan has started and it is under development.

2.4 Dissemination and Communication

The main paths and features of the communication activities related to the citizen engagement strategy and according to the planning under WP8 and the Valencia Local Communication Desk are finally designed in this document. The full dissemination and

communication strategy are described under the D8.1 Dissemination and Communication Plan and the features of the Local Communication Desk further specified, where needed.

Communication and Dissemination activities related to citizen engagement start in September 2018. However, during the elapsed time since the beginning of the project, the city of Valencia has made a special effort to spread the project, focusing on what is it about and in which areas of innovative actions will be carried out and where. The detailed description of the communication activities is in Chapter 6 on Dissemination and communication.

3 Ecosystem analysis

The aim of this section is to analyse the existing citizen engagement infrastructure and processes, in order to ensure the efficiency and effectiveness of the MAtchUP new citizen engagement strategies in the city of Valencia. The analysis is performed at the city and the district level.

Figure 5 - District object of the analysis

The district object of the analysis is POBLATS MARITIMS (district number 11 marked in red) where Valencia interventions will be performed. It is integrated by five subdistricts:

- ❖ Cabanyal-Canyamelar-Cap de França
- ❖ MalvaRosa
- ❖ Beteró
- ❖ Grau
- ❖ Nazaret

The district and its five subdistricts are analysed in the present document and will be the environment for the citizen engagement activities deployed.

3.1 Analysis of the existing citizen engagement infrastructure

In this epigraph we'll analyse the existing channels and sites available in the city and the district enabling the direct participation of citizens in the construction and implementation of policies, strategies and plans.

It is necessary to point out that the City Council of Valencia is currently (September, 2018) developing the regulation document that allows the implementation of the Citizen Participation Model of the City of Valencia. This model was designed together with the citizenry through a participatory process. This **regulation document** based on the new model will allow the development and implementation of a virtual and in-person infrastructure common to all districts of the city of Valencia.

3.1.1 Virtual

Virtual infrastructure such as online platforms, application software, collaborative channels having as a purpose the citizen engagement at all levels (Inform, Consult, Involve, Collaborate, Empower), in the district and/or in the four MAtchUP pillars: Energy, Mobility, ICT, Social.

In the district we do not find specific virtual spaces of participation, so we will refer to the infrastructure on a city scale, identifying those elements that we will be able to use within the MatchUP project.

This section does not include public services or information platforms that do not have the aim of active participation of citizens in decision-making processes.

3.1.1.1 #DecidimVLC

It is the platform in which is carried out the on-line participation of the citizenship of Valencia. This platform is based on the technology CONSUL, a tool developed by the City Council of Madrid in Open Source and adapted by the city Council of Valencia.

Figure 6. #DecidimVLC

Although the tool at this time is only used for the development of the "Citizen Consultation on Investments" (participatory budgets), it presents other features such as:

- Presentation and discussion of **Ideas**
- presentation and support of **Citizen Proposals**
- Co-drafting of **Collaborative Legislation**

At the current time (Sept 2018) the city council of Valencia is working on the development of new functionalities for the "citizen participation portal". From the project MatchUP will work with the managing service (Decentralization and Citizen Participation Service) to collaborate in its development.

The two following websites are informative, but they are relevant as they facilitate two cornerstones of any engagement process: transparency and information. On one side, the "Open Government" for the data access, visualization and download, and on the other side "Geoportal", allowing the data geopositioned visualization. Both platforms are managed by the Valencia municipality.

The "#decidimVLC" URL is: <http://decidimvlc.valencia.es>.

3.1.1.2 Open Government

The website allows the access, visualization and download of several data. The platform is structured in four sections, as follows:

1. Transparency
2. Good governance
3. Open data
4. Budget visualization

Figure 7. Open government website

The “Open Government” URL is: <http://gobiernoabierto.valencia.es/va/>.

3.1.1.2 Geoportal

The “Geoportal” allows the geopositioned visualization of data through interactive data of the Valencia municipality map, classified by area (Environment, Urban Planning, Tourism, Transport, Health, ...). Data on public services, such as public equipment and urban elements, or organizations and associations are also included.

Figure 8. GEOPORTAL website

The “Geoportal” URL is: <https://geoportal.valencia.es/home/>.

3.1.2 Face-to-face (F2F)

The face-to-face infrastructure is the governance infrastructure for the citizen engagement based in the district. These are spaces and participatory groups aimed at increase the citizens' influence on the decision making in the four MAtchUP pillars: Energy, Mobility, ICT, Social. In the following paragraphs the existing infrastructure is analysed, and the spaces and participatory groups that can be used within the MAtchUP citizen engagement strategy selected. The governance infrastructure is presented by domain: city and district domain.

3.1.2.1 City domain

The spaces and participatory groups that can be used in the district within the MAtchUP citizen engagement are marked with an asterisk *.

A. Sectoral Councils / *Consejos Sectoriales*

The sectoral councils are cross-territorial consultation bodies. In general, they meet twice a year, while extraordinary meetings take place when required. For the purpose of this analysis, only the bodies active from 2015 are taken into consideration.

- **Social** Council of the city / *Consejo Social de la ciudad de València* *
- **Food** Town Council / *Consejo Alimentario Municipal*
- Town Council of **Environment** / *Consejo Municipal de Medio Ambiente* *
- Town Council of **Cooperation** / *Consejo Municipal de Cooperación* *
- Local Council of **Immigration and Interculturality** / *Consejo Local de Inmigración e Interculturalidad* *
- Town Council of **Social Action** / *Consejo Municipal de Acción Social* *
- Town Council of **Women** / *Consejo Municipal de la Mujer* *

B. District Councils (territorial) / *Consejos de Distrito (territoriales)*

The District Councils (*Consejos de Distrito*) include political and civil society representatives and they are the consultation bodies of the District Boards (*Juntas de Distrito*). The District Boards are local administrative structures, they don't manage own budget but administrative procedures such as the register of inhabitants, travel cards, licences, among others. They are territorial bodies (i.e. each district has one) and they meet three times a year.

District Council of the District Board of / *Consejo de Distrito de la Junta de Distrito de:*

- Marítim** *
- Abastos**
- Ciutat Vella**
- Exposició**
- Patraix**
- Russafa**
- Trànsits**
- Pobles del Nord**
- Pobles del Sud**
- Pobles de l'Oest**

C. Working Groups (thematic in each territory) /

GRUPOS DE TRABAJO (temáticos en cada territorio).

Working groups on specific themes within the District Councils. They meet quarterly.

WGs of the District Council of **Marítim** *

- Urban planning, Mobility and Investments in Neighborhoods *
- Social Welfare *
- Culture
- Cohesion and Citizen Protection *

WGs of the District Council of **Abastos**

- Urban planning and Investments in Neighborhoods
- Social Welfare
- Culture

WGs of the District Council of **Ciutat Vella**

- Urban planning and Mobility
- Social Welfare

WGs of the District Council of **Exposició**

- Urban planning and Investments in Neighborhoods
- Social Welfare and Health
- Culture and Education
- Economic Activities

WGs of the District Council of **Patraix**

- Urban planning and Investments in Neighborhoods
- Social Welfare
- Culture

WGs of the District Council of **Russafa**

- Urban planning and Investments in Neighborhoods
- Social Welfare
- Culture

WGs of the District Council of **Trànsits**

- Urban planning and Investments in Neighborhoods
- Social Welfare and Citizen Security
- Culture

WGs of the District Council of **Pobles de l'Oest**

- Urban planning, Mobility and Investments in Neighborhoods
- Social Welfare and Citizen Security
- Culture

WGs of the District Council of **Pobles del Nord**

WGs of the District Council of **Pobles del Sud**

D. Ad hoc F2F spaces

Working groups and participatory bodies may be created for specific processes or projects. Currently, the Municipality is mapping all the existing bodies. Once the mapping is finalized, we will select the bodies relevant for the district and the MATCHUP engagement strategy. These bodies are:

- TECHNICAL-POLITICAL TABLE / MESAS TÉCNICO - POLÍTICAS
- POLITICAL-CITIZEN TABLE / MESAS POLÍTICO - CIUDADANAS
- TECHNICAL-CITIZEN TABLE / MESAS TÉCNICO - CIUDADANAS

E. New spaces

The "citizen participation model of the city of València" plans the creation of further spaces for participation, which are therefore expected but not available at the moment. Some of them are considered relevant to the MATCHUP engagement strategy. They are:

- OBSERVATORY OF PARTICIPACION OF THE CITY OF VALENCIA /
OBSERVATORIO DE PARTICIPACIÓN DE LA CIUDAD DE VALENCIA
- OBSERVATORIES DISTRICT / OBSERVATORIOS DE DISTRITO *
- DISTRICT OFFICES OF CITIZEN INFORMATION /
OFICINAS DE ATENCIÓN CIUDADANA A NIVEL DE DISTRITO *

F. CONNECTA networks/ Redes Connecta (Las Naves - Innovation)

The CONECTA networks are aimed to generate networking communities among the main actors of the quadruple helix of innovation on the following five strategic sectors:

- MOBILITY *
- ENERGY AND WATER *
- AGRO-FOOD
- HEALTH AND HEALTHY CITY
- CREATIVE AND CULTURAL INDUSTRY

G. Other networks

- VIT EMPRENDE, a network promoted by the Employment and Entrepreneurship Foundation of the Municipality of Valencia, and aimed at bringing together the entrepreneurial ecosystem of the city.

H. "Parla amb Joan Ribó"

Open space where proposals, suggestions, petitions or complaints can be forwarded to the mayor and the municipal government. This space is established as an active listening mechanism with the purpose of improving the management of the city.

3.1.2.2 District domain

A. DISTRICT COUNCIL OF THE MUNICIPAL BOARD OF POBLATS MARITIMS / CONSEJO DE DISTRITO DE LA JUNTA DE DISTRITO DE MARÍTIM

Composition

President: Glòria Tello Company
Vice President: Sandra Gómez López
Secretary: María José Iranzo Iranzo

Working Groups linked to MATCHUP

- Urban planning, Mobility and Investments in Neighborhoods *
- Social Welfare
- Coexistence and Citizen Protection

3.3 Analysis of participatory processes and tools deployed in the district

The aim of this section is to analyse processes and tools for the participation implemented in the district in the last four years (starting from 2014).

Relevant processes at this regards were found in the subdistricts from Poblats Maritims District: Cabanyal-Canyamelar-Cap de França, Nazaret and Grau. Furthermore, the participatory process #DecidimVLC, managed at the city level, was also considered relevant for its impact on the district.

For each process the following aspects were analysed: driving entity, used infrastructure, degree of public participation achieved (Inform, Involve, Consult, Collaborate, Empower), involved people, status, and evaluation outcomes.

3.3.1 Cabanyal-Canyamelar-Cap de França

The subdistrict Cabanyal-Canyamelar-Cap de França is today one of the most remarkable urban areas of the city of Valencia. Historically, it has been a maritime neighbourhood with a strong identity character, characterized by its architectural and urban heritage, its variety of own traditions, population mixture and civic vitality. The neighbourhood has been the subject of urban aggression that has significantly deteriorated its image, both internally and as a city, generating a strong physical and social degradation.

Figure 9 - The subdistrict Cabanyal-Canyamelar-Cap de França

3.3.1.1 VA CABANYAL

Va Cabanyal was the participatory process developed in the subdistrict of Cabanyal-Canyamelar-Cap de França for the elaboration of the Strategy for Sustainable and Integrated Urban Development (EDUSI), funded by 50% by ERDF and by 50% by the municipality. The aim of the strategy is the rehabilitation of the neighbourhood from a multidimensional approach that encompasses the physical, economic and social regeneration of the area.

Va Cabanyal followed a bottom up approach, with all the stakeholders invited to get involved in. Through this participatory process, neighbours, policy makers and economic stakeholders have brought together all their proposals to identify challenges and needs, drafting the necessary actions to succeed in the social and economic regeneration of the area.

Driving entity: Municipality of Valencia.

i. Used infrastructure

The process was structured around the following working groups:

- Driving Group (25-30 neighbours)

- Communication & Dissemination Working Group
- Technical & Political Working Group
- Monitoring Committee

Several participatory spaces were enabled, both virtual and F2F. The virtual spaces enabled were:

- ✓ Web (vacabanyal.org)
- ✓ Twitter (@VaCabanyal)
- ✓ E-mail (vacabanyal@gmail.com)

The F2F participatory spaces included the office where most working activities took place, interviews to relevant actors, and participatory workshops, as detailed below.

(1) Va Cabanyal Office: dissemination and work space.

(2) Interviews. Several interviews were performed with neighbours and experts. Besides, exploratory questionnaires were spread among neighbours and shops owners. The interviews and the questionnaires allowed to deepen the main issues of interest for the neighbourhood, prioritized along the analysis and diagnosis phases, to widen the participation channels and as an information/ data source on relevant themes.

(3) Workshops. Three large workshops open to participation were organized in order to involve citizen in the process of designing the urban strategy for the sub-district from the beginning. The workshops aimed at covering the three steps of the process, namely diagnosis, elaboration of proposals, prioritization and lines of action. Specific participatory activities were realized addressed to children (6-12yo), *Va Cabanyal Infantil*.

The working groups and participatory spaces detailed above collaborated in the process of strategy elaboration, structured along three progressive phases (see [FIGURE 7](#)).

- ✓ Analysis and diagnosis
- ✓ Elaboration of proposals
- ✓ Prioritization and lines of action

Furthermore, the strategy plans the creation of a Neighbourhood Office in charge of the coordination of the programmes and projects developing in the sub-district, setting the mechanisms for an efficient and binding citizen engagement.

ii. Achieved degree of participation

The methodology used and the several open channels for participation, allowed the engagement at all levels, from the lowest to the highest. Each person, group or entity decided how they wanted to be involved, from registering to a mailing list to be informed (Inform), to participate in the spaces and activities of consultation (Consult), to be involved in the working groups (Involve), to collaborate in the driving group and in the decision-making workshops (Collaborate).

iii. People involved

Several groups and individual were involved in the neighbourhood, including key actors from the quadruple helix, as shown in the Sociogram ([FIGURE 8](#)). Significant effort was dedicated to this end, in order to identify the relevant actors and to analyse the relationships among them, with the aim of ensuring the largest representativeness

across the neighbourhood. The neighbourhood has a strong associative and collaborative fabric, so that the participation levels had to be high.

iv. Status

Closed. Deploying period: September 2015 - December 2015.

v. Evaluation outcomes

An evaluation of the participatory process was performed, but it is not public.

None of the participatory spaces and channels developed under Va Cabanyal is currently active. See **FIGURE 10** and **FIGURE 11** for further details.

Figure 10. Va Cabanyal process

Figure 11. Va Cabanyal sociogram

3.3.1.2 PEC Cabanyal

The Cabanyal-Canyamelar Special Plan/ Plan Especial Cabanyal (PEC Cabanyal) is the planning tool defining the urban planning, land use and heritage management.

The current General Urban Development Plan/ Plan General de Ordenación Urbana (PGOU), approved in 1988, was developed by a Special Plan for Protection and Internal Reform (PEPRI) for the Cabanyal-Canyamelar area. The PEPRI was paralyzed in 2009, so a new plan is needed to face the challenges posed by the Valencian sea front.

The PEC Cabanyal is as of today (September 2018) under development and implies a participatory process open to public.

Driving entity: Municipality of Valencia.

i. Used infrastructure

The participatory process is structured around the following working groups:

- Driving Group (25-30 neighbours)
- Thematic Working Groups: cohesion and social inclusion; public space and environment; communication & dissemination; employment and training; housing.
- Technical & Political Working Group
- Monitoring Committee
- Coordination Committee, in charge of coordination of the ongoing neighbourhood urban plans (PEC-EDUSI-ARRU-PIP)

Several participatory spaces are enabled, both virtual and F2F. The virtual spaces enabled are:

- ✓ Web (<http://www.pecplaespecial.com>)
- ✓ Facebook (@PECPlaEspecial)
- ✓ E-mail (info@pecplaespecial.com)

The F2F participatory spaces include the office where most working activities take place, interviews to relevant actors, and participatory workshops and activities, as detailed below.

- (1) Participation Office: dissemination and work space.
- (2) Interviews. Several interviews are administered to neighbours and experts, in order to approach the context and set diagnosis lines and potential fields of action.
- (3) Workshops for decision making.
- (4) Infodays for dissemination and training.
- (5) Participatory urban drifting, in order to collect subjective perspectives and perceptions on the urban environment.

The working groups and participatory spaces detailed above collaborate in the process of strategy elaboration, structured along three progressive phases, as shown in the **FIGURE 10**:

- ✓ Information and diagnosis
- ✓ Pathways and strategies
- ✓ Preliminary proposal

Figure 12. PEC process

According to the participatory process outcome, the setup of the Local Office for the Integrated Management of the Renovation and PEC Implementation is expected. The

PEC local office would be in charge of designing the spaces and mechanisms for an efficient and binding citizen engagement, among other tasks.

ii. Achieved degree of participation

The methodology and the several open channels for participation, allow the engagement at all levels, from the lowest to the highest. Each person, group or entity can decide how they want to be involved, from registering to a mailing list to be informed (Inform), to participate in the spaces and activities of consultation (Consult), to be involved in the working groups (Involve), to collaborate in the driving group and in the decision-making workshops (Collaborate).

iii. People involved

The involved public is the same identified within the Va Cabanyal sociogram, shown in the previous paragraph. In fact, the working area and the involved public coincide in the two processes, Va Cabanyal and PEC Cabanyal.

iv. Status

The participatory phase is closed. The process is still open to allegations, until October 2018.

Participatory phase: July 2017 - February 2018.

Public exposition and allegations – forthcoming, date to be confirmed.

v. Evaluation outcomes

No evaluations were performed on the process as of today.

None of the participatory spaces and channels developed is currently active, except the Monitoring Committee, in charge of the information to the public and answering the allegations during the public exposition legal process.

3.3.2 Nazaret

Figure 13 - The Nazaret sub-district

Nazaret is the southern subdistrict of Poblats Marítims district. Its geographical location at the mouth of the Turia River has historically offered a privileged location with its own beach and surrounded by vegetable garden. This situation changes with the amplification of the Port, the construction of a multitude of infrastructures and the implementation of the logistics activities zone, since they completely isolate the neighborhood from the rest of the city. The construction of the Formula 1 circuit makes the situation even worse and ended up stripping Nazaret of the assets it had.

3.3.2.1 Collaborative elaboration of the neighbourhood strategy

The Integrated Strategy for Nazaret is initiated by the Valencia Municipality in order to guide the pathways and actions to develop in the next years in the neighbourhood. Accordingly, the municipality is planning similar participatory processes in other districts of the city, addressed to the elaboration of integrated strategies. This approach shifted the city model from a process of growth towards the periphery and related degradation of the agricultural area of the Huerta to a more sustainable rehabilitation aimed at the improvement of the living conditions in the urban environment instead.

Driving entity: Municipality of Valencia.

i. Used infrastructure

The participatory process is structured around the following working groups:

- Promoting Group (25-30 neighbours), including two sub-groups: associations and citizens.
- Thematic Working Groups: urbanism; housing and mobility; education, health and culture; cohesion, employment and economy.
- Technical Working Group, including the local administration staff in the neighbourhood, such as practitioners of the health centers, social workers, youth professionals, teachers, trainers, religious communities, and other entities of social work).
- Monitoring Committee, with representatives of the different demographic groups and the existing public and social resources.

Several participatory spaces are enabled, both virtual and F2F. The virtual spaces enabled are:

- ✓ Web (<http://www.estrategianatzaret.valencia.es>)

The F2F participatory spaces include interviews to relevant actors and participatory workshops and activities, as detailed below.

(1) Interviews. Several interviews are administered to neighbours and experts, in order to further clarify issues prioritized during the analysis and diagnosis phases, and to develop contents for the action plan.

(2) Workshops or open meetings for decision making, one for each phase of the process of strategy elaboration.

(3) Workshops dedicated to specific target groups (Roma, immigrants, youngsters, ...).

(4) Timelines.

The working groups and participatory spaces detailed above collaborate in the process of strategy elaboration, structured along three progressive phases:

- ✓ Participatory diagnosis
- ✓ Training
- ✓ Proposals, including action lines and actions

ii. Achieved degree of participation

The methodology and the several open channels for participation, allow the engagement at all levels, from the lowest to the highest. Each person, group or entity can decide how

3.3.3 Grau

Figure 15 - The Grao sub-district

The Grao sub-district is located in the center of the POBLATS MARITIMS, linked to the historic dock of the Port of Valencia. In the last decades it has suffered important transformations derived both from the expansion of the port and the construction of large urban infrastructures such as the bases of the America's Cup or the Formula 1 circuit. Currently, the Valencia City Council is developing a process of citizen appropriation and opening of the seafront of the port, reversing the privatization of public space resulting from the implementation of the infrastructure mentioned above.

3.3.3.1 "Marina voices" / "Veus de la Marina"

The participatory process "Veus de la Marina" is developed with the objective of collaboratively designing, together with citizens, the new toponyms and routes, as well as the new signage of the public spaces of La Marina de Valencia (esplanades, docks, streets, old foundations, etc.).

The aim is *to turn La Marina into a public space full of life, uses and connected to the city, with which citizens feel identified.*

Driving entity: Consorcio Valencia 2007, composed by representatives of the Municipality of Valencia, the Valencian Regional Government and the National Government.

i. Used infrastructure

Several participatory spaces are enabled, both virtual and F2F. The virtual spaces enabled are:

- ✓ Web, not specific of the participatory process (www.lamarinadevalencia.com)
- ✓ E-mail (veusdelamarina@marinadevalencia.com)
- ✓ Online forms

The F2F participatory spaces include interviews to relevant actors and participatory workshops for the decision making, as detailed below.

(1) Interviews. Several interviews are administered to neighbours and experts as an approach to the local context and deepening of issues raised during the workshops.

(2) Workshops for decision making.

The participatory spaces detailed above collaborate in the process of strategy elaboration, structured along three progressive phases:

- ✓ Technical analysis and diagnosis. To this end the following tools were used: field work and participant observation; interviews; online forms.

- ✓ Collective construction. To this end the following tools were used: four thematic workshops, two for each theme: identity and public spaces, collective memory; workshops in the educational center CEIP Las Arenas; online forms.
- ✓ Implementation of the actions.

ii. Achieved degree of participation

The methodology and the several open channels for participation, allow the engagement at all levels, from the lowest to the highest. Each person, group or entity can decide how they want to be involved, from registering to a mailing list to be informed (Inform), to participate in the spaces and activities of consultation (Consult), to be involved in the working groups (Involve), to collaborate in the promoting group and in the decision-making workshops and open meetings (Collaborate). The process was also a tool for empowering citizens, since the decisions taken were effectively implemented (Empower).

iii. People involved

The categories of actors involved are: neighbours, visitors, workers and entrepreneurs from La Marina. The detailed list of the people involved is not available.

iv. Status

Closed. Deploying period: April 2017 - May 2018.

v. Evaluation outcomes

Evaluations of the participatory process are not known.

The participatory spaces and channels developed are currently not active.

3.3.4 City domain

3.3.4.1 #DecidimVLC

Through the city platform #DecidimVLC several processes of participatory budgeting were implemented. However, the participatory processes were implemented at the district level across the city.

i. Used infrastructure

The process is structured around the web platform [www. Decidimvlc.valencia.es](http://www.Decidimvlc.valencia.es) and the working groups organized in the district.

The main participatory virtual spaces enabled are:

- ✓ Web (www.decidimvlc.valencia.es)
- ✓ Facebook (@decidimVLC)
- ✓ Twitter (@decidimVLC)
- ✓ E-mail (consultaciudadanadinversiones@valencia.es)

The district working group constitutes the F2F participatory space for this participatory process.

The working group and participatory spaces detailed above collaborate in the process structured along three progressive phases:

- ✓ Proposals and support

- ✓ Evaluation
- ✓ Ballot

ii. Achieved degree of participation

The methodology and the several open channels for participation, allow the engagement at different levels:

- Proposing investment projects individually or on behalf of an association
- Supporting the proposals presented
- Joining the District Working Groups, individually or on behalf of an entity/ association
- Voting

#DecidimVLC is an empowering tool since specific public investment is allocated on the decisions taken by citizens; the decisions taken are implemented. moreover, the tools available allow each person, group or entity to decide how they want to be involved, from following the website to be informed (Inform), to supporting proposals and/or voting (Consult), to be involved in the elaboration of proposals (Involve), to collaborate in the working groups or the collective proposals (Collaborate).

iii. People involved

The process is addressed to the inhabitants of the city of Valencia over the age of 16 years, and the participation mechanisms are put in place with this purpose.

iv. Status

Every year since 2015 (Calls 2015-2016 / 2016-2017 / 2017-2018 / 2018-2019).

v. Evaluation outcomes:

An evaluation of the participatory process was performed, but it is not public.

3.4 Analysis of key stakeholders

The stakeholders and services related to the city engagement strategy in the district relevant under the four MAtchUP pillars are mapped under this section. The several sources of information are taken into account for the purpose:

- Municipal register of associations
- Sociograms and lists of key actors developed within the participatory processes realized in the district (Va Cabanyal, PEC Cabanyal, Integrated Strategy for Nazaret, Marina's voices).
- Consultations to key stakeholders and experts in the district

Key actors are identified within the following profiles according to:

I. THE QUADRUPLE HELIX MODEL OF OPEN INNOVATION

- PUBLIC ADMINISTRATION / PUBLIC SERVICES
- PRIVATE SECTOR
- CITIZENS AND CIVIL SOCIETY ORGANIZATIONS
- RESEARCH AND UNIVERSITY

II. THE FOUR MATCHUP PILLARS

- ENERGY
- MOBILITY
- ICT
- SOCIAL

The key actors and services are listed in the following tables; other relevant actors and services located in the District are included in Annex I. Other relevant actors and services in the district.

3.4.1 Quadruple helix

3.4.1.1 Public Administration / Public Services

Municipal bodies

District Board of Marítimo / Junta de Distrito De Marítimo
District Council of Marítimo / Consejo de Distrito De Marítimo
Decentralization and Participation Service: Virginia Martín (Head of Service) / Servicio de Descentralización y Participación
MATCHUP Project Manager: Ernesto Faubel, Providing Connection with the rest of Municipal Services Involved in MATCHUP and its Representatives:
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Innovation Department / Serv. Innovación Trade and Supply Department / Serv. Comercio y Abastecimiento Employment and Entrepreneurship Department / Serv. Empleo y Emprendimiento Social Welfare and Integration Department / Serv. Bienestar social e Integración Urban Projects Department / Serv. Proyectos urbanos Infrastructure works Department / Serv. Obras de infraestructuras Housing Department / Serv. Vivienda Education Department / Serv. Educación - Sport Department and Municipal Sports Foundation / Serv. Deporte y Fundación Deportiva Municipal Circulation, Transport and its Infrastructures Department / Serv. Circulación, Transporte y sus Infraestructuras Cultural Heritage Department / Serv. Patrimonio cultural Cultural Resources Department / Serv. Recursos culturales Economic Promotion and Tourism Department / Serv. de Promoción económica y Turismo Information and Communication Technology Department (SERTIC) / Serv. Tecnología de la información y la Comunicación Environmental Quality Department / Serv. Calidad medioambiental
Plan Cabanyal Office: Vicent Gallart (Head of office)
AUMSA. Municipal Urban Performances / Actuaciones Urbanas Municipales S.A. Valencia
FOUNDATIONS:
Climate Change Foundation / Fundación Cambio Climático
Employment Pact Foundation / Fundación Pacto por el Empleo
OBSERVATORIES
Climate Change Observatory / Observatorio del Cambio Climático
Observatory for Employment / Observatorio para el empleo
LAS NAVES. Innovation center of Valencia

Regional bodies

GENERALITAT VALENCIANA (REGIONAL AUTHORITY):
Housing Department / Conselleria de Vivienda
Education Department - ITACA System / Conselleria de Educación
Sustainable economy and work / Conselleria de Economía Sostenible y Trabajo
SERVEF - Valencian Service of occupation and formation / Servei Valencià d'Ocupació i Formació
IVACE - Valencian Institute of Business Competition / Instituto Valenciano de la Competencia Empresarial
(IVE) VALENCIAN INSTITUTE OF BUILDING / INSTITUTO VALENCIANO DE LA EDIFICACIÓN

Public services: education, social and employment

	EDUCATION/ TRAINING	SOCIAL	EMPLOYMENT
CABANYAL-CANYAMELAR -CAP DE FRANÇA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> CEIP Las Arenas (primary) CEIP Serreria (primary) CAES Santiago Apóstol (private) (primary) Colegio Pureza de Maria (private) (primary) Colegio Chiner de Villaroya (private) (primary) Colegio Nuestra Señora del Rosario (private) (primary) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Centro de Menores de El Cabanyal (young people) Centro Municipal de Personas Mayores de El Cabanyal (adults) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Valencia Activa, Oficina de Marítimo (employment)
NAZARET	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> CEIP Juan Manuel Montoya (primary) CEIP Ausias March (primary) Colegio Nuestra Señora de los Desamparados (private) (primary and secondary) Colegio Santa Magdalena Sofia (privado) (La Punta) (primary) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Centro Municipal de Servicios Sociales de Nazaret (social services) Centro Especializado de Atención a Mayores de Nazaret (CEAM) (elderly people) Centro Municipal de Actividades Personas Mayores (CMAPM) (elderly people) Centro Municipal de Juventud de Nazaret (young people) 	
GRAU	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> IES Grao (secondary) IES Balears (secondary) CEIP El Grao (primary) CEIP San José de Calasanz (primary) Colegio La Purísima (private) (primary) Colegio Trafalgar (private) (primary) 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> COLLAB de Las Naves (Business incubator of social innovation)
MALVARROSA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> IES Isabel de Villena (secondary) CEIP Malvarrosa (primary) CEIP Ballester Fandos (primary) CEIP Blasco Ibáñez (primary) CEIP Cavite-Isla del Hierro (primary) Escuelas Pías Malvarrosa (private) (primary and secondary) Centro de Formación de Personas Adultas Malvarrosa (adults) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Centro de Día de Jóvenes Malvarrosa (young people) Centro de Servicios Sociales de la Malvarrosa (social services) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Taller Prelaboral para Jóvenes Malvarrosa (employment workshop)
BETERÓ	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> IES Serpis (secondary) IES Cabanyal (secondary) 		

3.4.1.2 Private sector

BUSINESS ASSOCIATIONS
Asociación de Comerciantes del Marítimo ACIPMAR Asociación de Vendedores del mercado de El Cabanyal. Asociación de Empresarios Playa de las Arenas
STARTUPS COL-LAB "LAS NAVES"
Ponverdeatuvecino
MATCHUP PARTNERS
ETRA WiTraC Kveloce I+D+i
OTHER BUSINESS
AEIOLUZ
OTHER INSTITUTIONS
La Marina de València Autoridad Portuaria
OTHER CENTERS
Lanzadera EDEM

3.4.1.4 Citizens and civil society organizations

	NEIGHBOURHOOD ASSOCIATIONS	OTHER ASSOCIATIONS	CITIZEN PLATFORMS	SELF-MANAGED SPACES	INITIATIVES
CABANYAL	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • AVV Cabanyal-Canyamelar • AVV Pavimar • AVV Llamosi-Remonta 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • AMPA (parents) Colegio de Las Arenas • Asociación de Jubilados y Pensionistas Cabañal (elderly) • Asociación Amas de Casa Tyrius del Marítimo (women) • Associació Brúfol (social) • Ateneu Marítim (cultural/building) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Salvem El Cabanyal • Milliorem El Cabanyal • Cabanyal Reviu • 15m Poblat Marítims 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Espai Veïnal Cabanyal • La Col·lectiva • Cabanyal Horta • CSOA La Fusteria • Ateneo Libertario • Espai Obert El Marítim 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cabanyal Intim • Cabanyal Arxiu Viu • CraftCabanyal • Radio Escalante 329
NAZARET	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • AVV Nazaret • AVV Nazaret Unido 	<p><i>Employment</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • AVFEN (Asociación Valenciana para el Fomento de Empleo Natzaret) • Proyecto Mare (fundación José María Haro) <p><i>Other</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Asociación de Jubilados y Pensionistas Marítimo (elderly people) • El Arca de Noé (social) • Asociación U-Manos de Integración para el Desarrollo Educativo (education) • Asociación Ágora Cultural (cultural) • Asociación Àmbit y Albergue Espai (social) • Associació de Dones Natzaret Portes a Fora (women) • Grupo Scout Iter-Natzaret (young people) 	-	-	-
GRAU	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • AVV Balears-Grau • AVV Grau-Port 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Asociación de Jubilados y Pensionistas del Puerto 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Litoral per al poble • 15M Poblados Marítimos 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Matraz 	
MALVARROSA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • AVV Amics de la Malva • AVV Malvarrosa-Poblados Marítimos 	-	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Malva Conviu 	-	-
BETERÓ	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • AVV Beteró 				

3.4.1.5 Research and university

POLYTECHNICAL UNIVERSITY OF VALENCIA / UNIVERSIDAD POLITÉCNICA DE VALÈNCIA (UPV)

Cátedra Transporte y Sociedad (UPV)
Cátedra Govern Obert (UPV)

UNIVERSITY OF VALENCIA / UNIVERSITAT DE VALÈNCIA (UV)

Cátedra Ciudad de València (UV)
IRTIC - Instituto Universitario de Investigación de Robótica y Tecnologías de la Información y Comunicación (UV)
INTRAS - Institut Universitari d'Investigació de Trànsit i Seguretat Viària (UV)

ITE. TECHNOLOGICAL INSTITUTE OF ENERGY / INSTITUTO TECNOLÓGICO DE LA ENERGÍA

3.4.3 MATCHUP Pillars

3.4.3.1 Energy

There have not been detected agents present in the district linked to Energy.

3.4.3.2 Mobility

- València Camina
- València en Bici
- Colecamins
- València per l'aire

3.4.3.3 ICT

There have not been detected agents present in the district linked to ICTs

3.4.3.4 Citizens

- Taula Solidaritat Malvarrosa (Comité Ciudadano Anti-Sida, Fundació Aixec, Fundació Dasyc, Associació Xarxa, Save The Children, Cooperació Social Universitaria , Fundació-Amigó, Asociación Ambient)
- Secretariado Gitano

4 Diagnosis

The Diagnosis phase, as **FIGURE 16** shows, allows defining the contextual basis for the Engagement Action Plan. To this end, as a first step the existing virtual and F2F infrastructures suitable for MAtchUP at the city and district level are selected, based on the Ecosystem analysis performed (Section 3), together with relevant key alliances. Besides, recommendations based on the input collected within the WS1. Diagnosis Launch Workshop, held in Valencia the 3rd of July 2018 under the WP1 activities (see D1.1) allow the fine-tuning of the engagement action plan. The level of participation required by the Lighthouse interventions is then analysed, in order to determine the level of engagement actions required under the Action Plan. The virtual and face to face infrastructure that have to be created in order to implement the engagement strategy (together with the existing ones) are finally designed.

Figure 16 - Phases of the Diagnosis

- Selection of existing infrastructures and key alliances
- Recommendations
- Level of participation entailed by LH interventions
- MAtchUP virtual and F2F infrastructure

4.1 Selection of existing infrastructure

Based on the analysis of the existing infrastructure, the bodies and spaces of participation existing and relevant for the MAtchUP process are selected, both the institutional and the resulting from previous participatory processes. The infrastructure identified will be involved in the MAtchUP citizen engagement strategy (see **FIGURE 17**).

	CITY DOMAIN	DISTRICT DOMAIN
F2F	MUNICIPALITY Social Council Environment Council Cooperation Council Immigration and Interculturality Council Social Action Council Women Council Maritim District Council WGs of the Maritim District Council (Urban planning, Social Welfare, Cohesion) District observatory	MUNICIPALITY Maritim District Council & WGs #DecidimVLC participatory budgeting
	LAS NAVES CONNECTA Mobility CONNECTA Energy & Water	
	VALENCIACTIVA VIT EMPRENDE	
	NOT AVAILABLE Ad hoc F2F-spaces (under mapping process) District observatories (expected) District office of citizen information (expected)	NOT AVAILABLE Va Cabanyal participatory process infrastructure (not active) PEC participatory process F2F infrastructure (not active) PEC Monitoring Committee (Cabanyal-Canyamelar-Cap de França) (expected) Integrated Strategy for Nazaret participatory process infrastructure (not active)
VIRTUAL	MUNICIPALITY #DecidimVLC Open Government Geoportal	MUNICIPALITY PEC participatory process virtual infrastructure #DecidimVLC participatory budgeting

Figure 17. Relevant existing infrastructure

Moreover, key alliances are identified, based on the analysis of the key stakeholders. A sociogram is used as a tool to identify key alliances, their action sets and feasibility.

The district sociogram is currently under development.

This district sociogram will allow to visualize the degree of affinity with the project objectives of each stakeholder and its capacity to influence in this context. Moreover, once the agents are mapped, the sociogram will allow us to establish action sets that will gather agents with common positions as well as possible conflicts existing in the territory.

Finally, through the sociogram feasible alliances will be identified, both for strengthen their connection or manage conflicts, and further relevant actors, missed in previous processes, targeted.

4.2 Recommendations for action planning

Under the MAtchUP WP1, the Workshop WS1 Diagnosis Launch Workshop was held in Valencia the 3rd of July 2018 (M10) under the WP1 activities (see D1.1), aimed at analysing the existing city plans, related to citizen engagement, among others.

During the workshop, the Model for the Citizen Participation of the city of Valencia was analysed and Strengths and Weaknesses identified. This analysis is very relevant to the present engagement strategy, providing orientations on how to take advantage of the strengths and opportunities, and how to address and improve the weaknesses.

Along the MAtchUP engagement process the strengths and opportunities should be taken into account, and the weaknesses addressed in order to consolidate the strategy for the Project and further development.

STRENGTHS / Positive Aspects

Several participatory processes were implemented in the district, reaching medium- high participation levels (Involve and Collaborate), as mentioned above and as highlighted along the WS1.

- ✓ VA CABANYAL
- ✓ PEC CABANYAL
- ✓ Integrated Strategy for Nazaret
- ✓ Marina Voices
- ✓ DecidimVLC participatory budgeting in Poblats Maritims

Therefore, the public is mature for collaboration activities, but it has also high expectations and may suffer some burden proceeding from previous processes.

Besides, the previous participatory processes provided wide and relevant data and contents related to the planning in the district.

WEAKNESSES / Negative Aspects

The following weaknesses should be taken into consideration along the engagement strategy and the elaboration of the next regulatory model for the citizen participation.

- Lack of methodological frameworks to develop the mechanisms planned according to the participation model.
- Lack of evaluations (quantitative and qualitative) of some participatory processes and their public presentation.
- The evaluations carried out on previous processes and experiences are not identified and systematized.
- The evaluation and monitoring mechanisms are not defined.
- The territorial diagnoses of some districts are missing.
- Mechanisms or structures for the promotion of the internal participation among the personnel of the municipal administration are not designed (interdepartmental groups).
- The existing sectoral and intersectoral roundtables are not identified (in process).
- The implemented participation processes did not put in place measures or tools for the inclusion of people with some functional disability or with special necessities.

OPPORTUNITIES

The following opportunities should be taken into consideration along the engagement strategy and the elaboration of the next regulatory model for the citizen participation.

- Incorporation of "non-institutionalized" forms of participation.
- Introduction of other media for communication, engagement and transparency, such as the radio or TV (MatchUp channel).
- New features for #DecidimVLC.
- Detailed development of digital information, participation and communication tools.

4.4 Degree of participation of the Demonstration actions

4.4.1 The participation levels model

The citizens' engagement process in Valencia will entail different levels of public participation, based on the Spectrum of Public Participation developed by the International Association of Public Participation (IAP2) (FIGURE 18).

The Spectrum ranges from low participation, where people are simply informed about the relevant problems and alternative solutions (on websites for example) to high, where they are empowered to take the final decision on the issue at hand (i.e., through citizen juries or referendums) (Ostling, 2016).

Figure 18. Levels of participation.

Source: <http://tompkinscountyny.gov/tccp/publicparticipation>.

The five levels proposed are discrete degrees, not steps, lacking a hierarchy between them: each level can be appropriate depending on the context and which stage is chosen depends on the characteristics of the planned actions. However, the further to the right on the Spectrum, the more influence citizens have over decisions, and the stages can be interpreted as being progressive (Grace, 2007).

The IAP2 Spectrum works well together with the Enabling Change framework to guide about the appropriate level of engagement. Enabling Change (Robinson, 2018) offers a useful matrix to understand when a certain level of engagement is adequate according to the level of complexity, and perceived sensitivity of the action. Straightforward actions of minimal sensitivity or risk may need little more than good information being provided to all stakeholders. However, proposals which are complex and require time and discussion to fully understand, and which also carry significant levels of perceived risk or sensitivity, need processes which offer more involvement to stakeholders.

Figure 19. Consultation matrix.

Source: Les Robinson, 2002.

4.4.2 The participation levels of the Demonstration actions

The citizen engagement strategy to deploy in the Valencia is based on the different levels of engagement entailed by the LH interventions according to the two models described above.

The interventions planned in Valencia were therefore analysed together with the technical partners in charge, and the level of participation selected according to the goals of the actions, their complexity and their sensitivity.

In order to understand the features and requirements of the actions, and to establish the level of participation entailed, data were collected from partners through an ad hoc questionnaire². The data collected were validated during the WP2 meetings.

INFORM

Citizen engagement goal: To provide the public with balanced and objective information to assist them in understanding the problem, alternatives, opportunities and/or solutions.

Promise to the public: We will keep you informed.

² The G-Form questionnaire can be consulted [here](#).

Information only involves a one-way flow of information from the administration to citizens, nevertheless it is an important foundation for community engagement since it builds knowledge and allows citizens to understand the public decision-making process and to take informed decisions.

The Inform level is appropriate in situations where there is no opportunity for the public to influence decision-making and simply informing them is the appropriate activity. The inform level of public participation requires to give citizens what they need to fully understand the action and decision and to reach their own conclusions as to the appropriateness and adequacy of the decision.

Information is so important for the citizens' engagement, intended as the involvement in the decision making and policies processes, that some authors suggest even to consider that the Inform level should be placed across the Spectrum, demonstrating that effective engagement requires a strategic flow of information (Chappell, 2016). Indeed, all the relevant stakeholders (administration, business, academia, civil society) will be targeted at the Inform level about all the Lighthouse interventions in Valencia. Moreover, public demonstration sites will be used for exposition and training purposes, through open visits and seminars on site. They are listed in the **TABLE 3**:

	<p>ENERGY. A.9.Civic centre; A.11.Retrofitting of urban development local agency; A.13.Pilot Wave Energy Converter ; A.14.Sewerage energy recovery system; A.26.humble lampposts (10).</p>
	<p>MOBILITY. A.23.2multimodal hubs; A.25.Management of EV parking places.</p>
	<p>ICT. A.29.Smart District Energy Management System (SDEMS); A.32.IoT data integration with the VLCi smart city platform.</p>
	<p>CITIZENS. A.36.50/50 Programmes; A.41.District refurbishment local investment fund; A.46.Local toolkit for development of NZE Buildings; A.47.Local toolkit for RES production, storage, self-consumption; A.50.City Mentoring.</p>

Table 3 - Demonstration sites

 CONSULT

Citizen engagement goal: To obtain public feedback on analysis, alternatives and/or decisions.

Promise to the public: We will keep you informed, listen to and acknowledge concerns and provide feedback on how public input influenced the decision.

The Consult level of public participation focuses on feedback and is the basic minimum opportunity for public input to a decision: the administration obtains feedback about plans, ideas, options or issues, but with little interaction.

The Consult level is appropriate when specific input is sought from citizens for the decision making, but early engagement is not possible throughout the process.

Several Lighthouse interventions in Valencia require the willingness of citizens to provide information, especially on their energy consumption and behaviour, and the energy performance of their houses, in order to improve the energy efficiency and reduce costs. The interventions are in fact part of a wider strategy of high-performance district, including the integration of RES into the buildings, as well as passive solutions (Energy), together with monitoring and control through ICT integration (ICT), and they require the awareness (information) and input from the public (consultation). Moreover, several of these actions require the installation of devices within residential buildings, and the access to them (TABLE 4); this level of participation, provided that the action was already defined and citizens were not involved in it (decision making), was thus considered as Consult level. This applies to the energy interventions A1-A6 and the related A28 under the ICT pillar. Mobility interventions A17-A19 and A22 also require input from neighbours in the district on needs and habits related the services offered by ebikes (A17, A22) and access to residential buildings for the charging points (A18, A19).

	<p>ENERGY.</p> <p>A.1.Reconstruction of 16 houses; A.2. PVintegration 223kW; A.3.Electrical storage for self-consumption 1100 kWh model integr.; A.4.400 Smart meters; A.5.150 smart-controls; A.6.retrofitting of 548 private houses; A.12.Solar thermal integration.</p>
	<p>MOBILITY.</p> <p>A.17.5 e-bikes (2 for disabled mobility, 3 for last mile logistics); A.18.72 EV charging points; A.19.3 V2G pilots; A.22.Last mile logistics based on e-bikes.</p>
	<p>ICT.</p> <p>A.28.Smart Home Energy Management System (SHEMS).</p>

Table 4 - Actions to be performed which require the instalation of devices

 INVOLVE

Citizen engagement goal: To work with the public to make sure that concerns and aspirations are considered and understood.

Promise to the public: we will work with you to ensure that your concerns and aspirations are directly reflected in the alternatives developed and provide feedback on how public input influenced the decision.

At the Involve level, citizens are invited into the process to a greater extent than with Consult: the goal is to work with the public throughout the process, it is a two-way exchange of information that encourages discussion and provides an opportunity to influence the outcome. The Involve level implies processes ensuring there is common understanding of the issue and that citizens views, concerns and aspirations are reflected in the development of options or approaches.

At the Involve level, the public is invited into the process, usually from the beginning, and is provided multiple if not ongoing opportunities for input as decision-making progresses. While the promise implies that issues raised should be taken into account, decisions at this level are generally made by the administration rather than the public.

The Involve level is appropriate when people have some investment in an issue, but it is not very controversial nor has major implications for other people.

COLLABORATE

Citizen engagement goal: To partner with the public in each aspect of the decision-making.

Promise to the public: We will look to you for direct advice and innovation in formulating solutions and incorporate your advice and recommendations into the decisions to the maximum extent possible.

At the Collaborate level, the public is directly engaged in decision-making and it is involved in an interactive process with an emphasis on two-way processes. The Collaborate level of citizen engagement includes all the elements of Involve but takes it a step further. Collaborate often includes the explicit attempt to find consensus solutions. However, similar to the Involve level of participation, the administration is still the ultimate decision-maker. The degree to which consensus will be sought and how much decision authority the administration will be willing and able to share must be made explicit.

At this level it is important to create trust and to ensure that there is genuine engagement and this can be costly and time-consuming. Besides, there can be risks involved in processes at this level. If the promise is seen as being broken (e.g., if members of a community cannot agree of ways forward, or if some sections of the community feel their views were not taken into account), trust can be broken and future relationships with key stakeholders can be significantly damaged. Collaborate is particularly useful for controversial issues and complex problems because it entails a high level of participation.

Most of the non-technical interventions, dealing with innovative businesses, urban planning and citizens' engagement imply the participation of the public at some point and to some extent, including the participation in the decision making process in some cases (TABLE 5). These actions therefore can be placed across the Involve and Collaborate levels, which some authors define the Deliberate level, and the engagement activities should be defined accordingly.

	<p>CITIZENS. A.34.City policies update; A.35.Employment initiative; A.37.Social & local entrepreneurship program; A.38.Business opportunities; A.39.Shared PP investment models; A.40.Prosumer energy cooperatives; A.42.Upscaling plan; A.45.Citizen engagement; A.48.Local strategy to mitigate energy poverty.</p>
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Table 5 - Actions specifically focused on Citizens' Engagement

The level of participation of the interventions aimed at policy improvements is still to determine.

EMPOWER

Citizen engagement goal: To place final decision-making in the hand of the public.

Promise to the public: We will implement what you decide.

At the Empower level, the public has the opportunity to make decisions for themselves.

It does not necessarily mean it is the highest level of community engagement. Whereas Collaborate requires a high level of community engagement, Empower does not necessarily require the same degree of community engagement. At this level, a decision could be made by the community through a process that requires little interaction or engagement (e.g., a referendum). The most common activities at this level are public voting or ballot measures.

Governments rarely conduct public participation at the Empower level because of a perception that they are not permitted to delegate their decision-making authority to the public. However, the promise of the Empower level is not about statutory authority but a promise to *implement what you decide*. Responsibility for the decision can still lie with the elected body while honouring the promise (Susskind, 2008). Indeed, the MATchUP engagement approach is based on empowering citizens by giving some authority and power in the decision-making process.

Under the Citizen engagement intervention, citizens may be involved in prioritizing district needs and requirements through open participatory activities, and they could work on proposals through online consultations.

	<p>CITIZENS. A.45.Citizen engagement.</p>
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The level of participation of the Valencia Lighthouse interventions are summarized in the **FIGURE 20:**

LH Intervention					
A.1	✓		✓		
A.2	✓		✓		
A.3	✓		✓		
A.4	✓		✓		
A.5	✓		✓		
A.6	✓		✓		
A.7	✓				
A.8	✓				
A.9	✓	✓			
A.10	✓				
A.11	✓	✓			
A.12	✓		✓		
A.13	✓	✓			
A.14	✓	✓			
A.26	✓	✓			
A.27	✓				
A.15	✓				
A.16	✓				
A.17	✓		✓		
A.18	✓		✓		
A.19	✓		✓		
A.20	✓				
A.21	✓				
A.22	✓		✓		
A.23	✓	✓			
A.24	✓				
A.25	✓	✓			

LH Intervention						
		INFORM	DEMO	CONSULT	INV&COLL	EMPOWER
A.28		✓		✓		
A.29		✓	✓			
A.30		✓				
A.31		✓				
A.32		✓	✓			
A.33		✓				
A.34		✓			✓	
A.35		✓			✓	
A.36		✓	✓			
A.37		✓			✓	
A.38		✓			✓	
A.39		✓			✓	
A.40		✓			✓	
A.41		✓	✓			
A.42		✓			✓	
A.43		✓				
A.44		✓				
A.45		✓			✓	✓
A.46		✓	✓			
A.47		✓	✓			
A.48		✓			✓	
A.49		✓				
A.50		✓	✓			
A.51		✓				
A.52		✓				

Figure 20. Level of public participation in LH interventions- Valencia

4.5 Definition of the MAtchUP virtual window

The following virtual channels and sites will be used for the MAtchUP citizen participation.

Web platforms

- MAtchUP website (<http://www.matchup-project.eu/>) - active
- MAtchUP local website – under construction
- #DecidimVLC – link to MAtchUP under construction

Social networks

Twitter (@matchupEU)

Other social networks at the project or local level will be studied and built, if relevant, by the Communication Local Desk, according to the Communication Strategy (see Chapter 6).

In particular, with reference to the websites, the partners in charge of the Communication Local Desk (LNV, VAL), the Engagement strategy (KVEL) and the Municipal Decentralization and Participation services are working together in order to identify synergies and connections. In particular, the virtual infrastructure envisaged for the engagement process under MAtchup will be based on the main MAtchUP website, for the general dissemination of the project; the local MAtchUP website, with full and detailed information on the LH interventions; finally, the implementation of MAtchUP online participatory processes, such as proposals, forum, ballots, among others, hosted by the current municipal website devoted to participation (#DecidimVLC). In particular, the local

MATCHUP website and #DecidimVLC will be connected, and the technical features are at the present date under development.

The planned structure is shown in **FIGURE 21**, **FIGURE 22** and **FIGURE 23**:

Figure 21. MATCHUP Virtual Infrastructure

#Decidim VLC, as mentioned above, is the virtual platform for the citizens' participation of the City of Valencia. The platform is based on the technology CONSUL, a tool developed by the City Council of Madrid in Open Source and adapted by the city Council of Valencia. #DecidimVLC is currently under a process of widening its features. Among others, the connection to ongoing projects entailing participatory processes is planned. Therefore, a connection to MATCHUP and related participatory actions is planned and under analysis for development. The connection will be on one side addressed (1) to provide information on the project engagement activities and, on the other side, (2) to host MATCHUP online participatory processes, where needed, in #DecidimVLC, as shown in the **FIGURE 22**.

Figure 22. MAtchUP Virtual Infrastructure (#DecidimVLC)

The MAtchUP local website will host information on the LH interventions that will be implemented in Valencia, and detail on each action, including resources, events and associated participatory activities. The VLC Open Data will be visualized and/or hosted. As said, when needed, the MAtchUP local website will address the user to the participatory platform #DecidimVLC, as shown in the [FIGURE 23](#).

The information will be available in Spanish and Valencian.

Figure 23. MAtchUP Virtual Infrastructure (local website)

4.6 Definition of the MAtchUP F2F infrastructure

The F2F infrastructure designed for the MAtchUP citizen engagement strategy is showed in **FIGURE 24**.

Figure 24. MAtchUP F2F infrastructure

MATchUP Meeting Point. This will be the site of the MATchUP participation activities. The aim is to provide information on the project and LH interventions and to host the participatory events, seminars, workshops and meetings. The MATchUP Meeting Point will be the point of reference and development of the Project and it will serve as:

- ❖ The working place of the Coordination and Management Group (CMG), in charge of the coordination and management of the citizen engagement strategy;
- ❖ The central office for the Communication and Dissemination of the activities developed. The Local Communication Desk may be located here;
- ❖ The meeting point and debate among the sectoral committees, technicians, the citizens, research institutions and the experts from the municipality;
- ❖ The site for the development of assemblies, workshops and meetings.

Weekly Meeting “Dijous MATchUP”. As a permanent and visible space for meeting, the MATchUP staff for the citizen engagement will be available to the public once per week (the so called “Dijous MATchUP”). The weekly event Dijous MatchUP will be hosted on a rotating basis across the five neighbourhood of the district. The contents of the event will vary according to the status and needs of the LH interventions and the participatory process, and may include: driving group meetings; meetings between LH interventions technical partners and neighbours; meetings with other key actors linked to the interventions (EDUSI, PIP, ARRU, PACSA, Employment Pact Foundation, SERVEF, etc.); information and news on the implementation of the interventions; training.

Coordination and management group

The Coordination and Management Group (CMG), is composed by facilitators and technical partners who will be responsible of the contents and methodology throughout the whole process. The CMG Group establishes, since the start of the strategy, agile and flexible governance systems that will allow good communication and coordination towards citizens, technicians, policy makers and stakeholders.

It coordinates the different bodies and groups created for the engagement process. It also acts as a mediation team maintaining fluid communication and a close and continuous collaboration with the social and economic agents, addressing the problems that may arise from the confluence of divergent interests.

Driving Group

Composition: CITIZENS + COORDINATION & MANAGEMENT TEAM.
Objective: Dynamization, information, training, coordination of the working groups.
Frequency of the meetings: to be confirmed.

It is constituted by the citizens and volunteers; and the technical group of management and coordination. The Driving Group is active along the whole process, is composed by people really engaged and who take on responsibility part of the process. This group of people is at the same time source of information and the centre of the process. The Driving Group is flexible, and new members can be invited whenever specific issues and themes require it. The DG may support in the data collection on their referring environments, on existing networks and relationships. The DG is able to self-manage many of the actions and initiatives that arise from the process.

Sectoral Committees

Composition: THEMATIC WORKING GROUPS + STAKEHOLDERS + CITIZENS.

Objective: proposals elaboration, debates, reflection, training.

Frequency of the meetings: self-managed with support where needed.

These commissions work in specific domains and they are composed by technicians, expert in the field. They are groups already working in the district (i.e. the identified WGs of the District Council), or under MAtchUP (such as the Thematic Working Groups managed under WP1) and/or created answering to specific needs and interests. Further Sectoral Commissions may be created around a specific MAtchUP performance, or depending on other needs or interests linked to the program. The Communication and Dissemination Group is also a specific sectorial committee, dedicated to ensuring a correct connection with the citizens of the field and the transparency of the process.

Spaces of decision making

Composition: THEMATIC WORKING GROUPS + DRIVING GROUP + CITIZENS + STAKEHOLDERS.

Objective: decision making, prioritization.

Frequency of the meetings: 3-4 times/ year, when needed.

When working groups and sectoral committees make proposals that need an open space of decision for all the citizens, specific spaces of decision making need to be set up. In these spaces, the proposals are legitimized and priority is given to the most urgent actions and proposals to work in the medium and long term.

Monitoring Committee

Composition: DRIVING GROUP + CITIZENS + STAKEHOLDERS

Objective: monitoring, transparency, dialogue with public administration.

Frequency of the meetings: quarterly.

The monitoring committee is integrated by:

- ✓ Policy makers
- ✓ Process Promoters
- ✓ Representative associations
- ✓ Driving Group

This committee is informed during all the participative process. It is an essential part of the participatory process of defining the strategy, working as a supervisor of the negotiation in some pivotal moment and ensuring the transparency and the proper functioning of the citizens' involvement process. A fluid and continuous communication should be guaranteed between all the agents of the monitoring committee and in addition, control and information meetings are to be established.

The launch of the MAtchUP infrastructure is scheduled for December 2018 (M15), in occasion of the **City Needs and Priorities Workshop** (see the MAtchUP CE Strategies, p. 12 of this document, and D1.1, WP1).

5 Action Plan

5.1 City needs and priorities Workshop (WS3)

As mentioned above, under WP1, T1.1 City Advanced Characterization (related in D1.1) a participatory workshop is planned at M15, the **City needs and priorities workshop** (at city level). This workshop will be used as an open public event for the launch of the MAtchUP demonstration in Valencia and it will be held in the district area. The workshop is aimed at identifying collaboratively the interest, opinions, and wishes from the public and at prioritizing the citizens' needs, in order to align the interventions to citizens' needs and priorities.

The results of the City needs and priorities workshop will further nurture the planning of the Citizen Engagement activities.

5.2 Citizen Engagement activities

The activities and tools that are to be developed will be finally agreed with the district citizens during the Workshop WS3. However, this first version of the Citizen Engagement Strategy (D2.12) includes a preliminary list of activities suitable for each level of participation, summarized in the **FIGURE 25** and listed below. Further details will be defined in the next phases of the process.

Figure 25. Public participation toolkit.

Source: <http://tompkinscountyny.gov/tccp/publicparticipation>

5.2.1 Inform

Inform: to provide balanced and objective information in a timely manner.

Activities under this level of participation may include:

- Information
- Communication
- Education & Training

Further information are provided under Chapter 6. Dissemination and Communication

5.2.2 Consult

Consult: to obtain feedback on analysis, issues, alternatives and decisions.

Activities under this level of participation entail one- way interactions, and may include:

- Surveys
- Polling

5.2.3 Involve

Involve: to work with the public to make sure that concerns and aspirations are considered and understood.

Activities under this level of participation entail two- way interactions, and may include:

- Interviews
- Timeline
- Focus groups
- Forum Online
- Special training activities

5.2.4 Collaborate

Collaborate: to partner with the public in each aspect of the decision-making.

Activities under this level of participation entail repeated and iterative interactions and creative feedback techniques, and may include:

- Sociogram
- Collaborative mapping
- EASW
- SWOT
- Tetralemma
- Flow Chart
- Tree of problems
- Driving Idea

- Pop-up events

5.2.5 Empower

Empower: to place final decision-making in the hand of the public.

The development of stable participation, monitoring and evaluation structures that have competencies and decision-making capacity should be setup in order to work across the Empower level. Collaborative work and decision making spaces may be developed through:

- Co-design of the decision making process
- Collaborative building of the diagnosis, objectives and actions
- Collaborative building of monitoring and evaluation indicators
- Activities for the setup of permanent structures for the collaboration and coordination within the public administration and with external actors.

5.3 Monitoring

It would be desirable to establish monitoring devices throughout the MATCHUP project implementation process. These devices must contain criteria and indicators not just technical or quantitative, but also incorporate others defined in a more qualitative and participatory way.

The propose of both indicators' batteries (technical and citizens) is to be able to rectify and adapt the actions to the context and the specific time in which they must be developed, taking advantage of the opportunities (overflows) that appear during the implementation. This non-stop evaluation will allow us to certain conditions that do not coincide or were not considered in the initial situation during the performance of the actions.

It would be important to operationalize the monitoring process so that it can document, systematize, communicate and disseminate the information and learn about it.

In this sense it will be important to monitor not only the progress and results that the implementation of the actions will produce but as well, we would have to monitor the participation itself, with its own criteria and indicators. Again, these indicators will have to be both quantity and quality. It is important not to forget the cultural criteria that will indicate if we are reaching all sectors of the population of the district or there are population groups that are being excluded.

As tools for this monitoring we can use:

- Schedules
- Cohereniometers
- “Targets” tracking
- “Rubrics” tracking
- Monitoring tracking

5.4 Evaluation

The evaluation of the implementation process of MatchUp will be one of the points in which it will be necessary to pay special attention. It would be advisable to introduce in addition to the technical evaluation, which aims to meet objectives set by the project, a more participatory evaluation that involves citizens and allows us to collectively analyse the results and the impact it is having on the population.

In this sense, and as we indicated in the previous section, it is important to differentiate between two types of evaluations that must occur simultaneously. On the one hand, the evaluation of the participatory process itself, and on the other, the evaluation of the impacts at the local level.

The indicators that are established for the evaluation must address the objectives in the short, medium and long term. These indicators can cover areas such as: type of agent involved and their degree of involvement, degree of self-management of the devices and established participation groups (motor group, work groups...), degree of legitimacy perceived in the decision spaces, etc)

As tools for the monitoring we can use:

- Evaluation "targets"
- Evaluation "rubrics"
- Indicators of evaluation of participation
- Impact assessment indicators.

5.5 Gantt Diagram

Figure 26. Gantt Diagram

6 Dissemination and communication

Communication and Dissemination activities related to citizen engagement have started in September 2018. However, from the very beginning of the project, the city of Valencia has made a special effort to spread the project, focusing on its objectives and on the areas on innovation.

Therefore, we have invested a lot on social and online dissemination during every event and city where the project has been introduced, both in Valencia and in other cities. Furthermore, current D&C materials, like the flyer, the newsletter and the video, have been widely disseminated.

The most important contents of the actions have been sent to the local and national media to publish them. In order to reach and engage citizens, we have opted for a clear and simple communication with the aim to get catchy messages to engage citizens and local authorities.

Once explained to citizens the general aim of the project, we will proceed to segment the actions according to the degree of citizen involvement and the type of public. For this, we are currently evaluating several ways to engage the public, from dedicated and programmed marketing campaigns to informative actions dedicated to the whole city of Valencia.

6.1 Approach

Communication covers a wide range of actions targeted to several stakeholders or target audiences, and should also communicate evidence-based information about areas and contents directly related with the project, being those produced by the consortium or by third-parties. The most important objective (primary objective) is to engage citizens; secondarily, it is intended to engage and involve several stakeholders: research community, public administration, companies or investors, among others, to be detailed in the section 6.3.3 and in the table specifying the communication campaigns to be carried out in Valencia in the section 6.4. A Responsible Innovation Communication must select, curate and disseminate contents based on validated information but making easily affordable for all.

The communication activity within MAtchUP in Valencia will allow to collect data and distribute information, even from third parties, in order to optimise the engagement rate of all target groups potentially reached, including citizenship, investors, public administration officers and any other group susceptible to be considered as a multiplier entity (eg., civil society entities, NGOs, associations, foundations, cultural centres, libraries, etc.).

6.2 Local Communication Desk

In order to sustain the communication activity in Valencia, the Valencian Local Communication Desk was established, including personnel from VAL, LNV and KVEL.

The following table identifies the main organizational aspects of the Valencian Local Communication Desk are described: composition (team members and their role); relation with other institutional bodies; relation with MAtchUP partners and WPs.

Team members and their role	M ^a José Perales, Communication Officer (LNV) Barbara Branchini, Project Manager (KVEL) Fran Azorín, Citizen Engagement Expert (KVEL) Beatriz Vallina, Communication Officer (KVEL)
Relation with other institutional bodies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Agència Valenciana de la Innovació - AVI ▪ Asociación Valenciana Empresas Sector Energía - AVAESEN ▪ CLIMATE KIC Valencia ▪ Centro Europeo de Empresas e Innovación de Valencia - CEEI Valencia ▪ Fundación Ecología y Desarrollo - ECODES ▪ Ciudad Politécnica de la Innovación - CPI-UPV ▪ Red de Institutos Tecnológicos de la Comunidad Valenciana - REDIT ▪ Instituto Tecnológico de la Construcción - AIDICO ▪ Cluster de Energía de la Comunidad Valenciana ▪ Mesa de la Movilidad de Valencia ▪ Asociación Valenciana del Vehículo Eléctrico - AVVE
Relation with MAtchUP partners and WPs	ICE (WP8) WP2 partners (WP2) Fundación Cambio Climático

The Local Communication Desk is in charge of the local D&C strategy definition, including, identification of appropriate channels, messages and specific social media and communication formats to foster engagement.

6.3 Communication Strategy

In-line with the approach above, the communication strategy should be considered as:

- **Plan:** a intended course of action and a set of guidelines and actions for strategically approaching the citizens engagement.
- **Perspective:** a macro view of the strategy that involves planning, plotting, patterning, and positioning but after defining the outcome, that is engagement.

Engagement is a term widely used in the literature; **in order to differentiate the term as used in the Action Plan and in the literature about communication itself**, it must be clarified that “engagement” in Communication refers to the community and aims at reaching a long-term alliance and loyalty with a certain audience (Holt and Chambers 2017). Engagement is not restricted to the interaction, the participation in the pilot phase, or the involvement during a predefined period, while these could be considered as dimensions or outputs: engagement means a medium and long-term sustainable relationship with feasible changes at the behavioural level. In addition, the engagement of audiences contributes to sustainability of MatchUp at medium and long-term (Hanson, Salmoni, and Volpe 2009).

How to engage targets seems to be the most difficult question to answer in this sense; this strategy considers that a multi-channel approach merging traditional and innovative media could contribute to accomplish the objective as expressed in the project proposal. So, among others, Valencian partners will attend and organise special events, use their

networks and personal influence through interpersonal and direct communication, social media and also traditional press and mass media (at local level, in-line with the project scope). Actions planned are furtherly detailed in Section 5.2. Consequently, the communication strategy should consider:

- opposition research
- specific audience targeting
- constant adjustment of the messages, when needed and observed through
- continuous follow-up and tracking of actions and response.

In addition, attention must be paid to key message, the mean for message delivering, audience's reactions, if observable, and unintended results. For online communication, "engagement" will be measured as the rate resulting from impressions³ and actions⁴.

6.3.1 Situation Analysis

Before designing a communication strategy, current means, communities and resources available should be clarified. In the case of Valencia, the current media that could be used and optimised are:

- -Policy learning platforms
- -Website
- -Social Media
- -Newsletter
- -Press and News Releases
- -Events and conferences

During the formative phase and the iterative cycles for evaluating the communication strategy and campaigns performance, qualitative and quantitative data should be collected:

- Concepts, definition, characteristics, interests, symbols and language should be qualitatively analysed during the whole project to improve the communication campaigns' design and results
- Figures, rates and any other quantitative information could be collected in order to numerically evaluate the performance of the communication strategy and its campaigns.

³ An impression is when a publication (then, ads, articles, links, pictures, etc.) is fetched from its source, and is countable, regardless people performs an action or not. It could be defined as "times seen"

⁴ An action is when an individual performs some activity over a material or publication: e.g., read a flyer or a poster, like the content on Social Media, open an article on a website, etc.

6.3.2 Goal/objectives

A clear analysis of the situation leads to specifying the overarching goal and objectives that should be addressed by the campaign. Goals are broad targets. Objectives are more specific.

In sum, the goal is to recruit and engage the Valencian citizenship, as it is furtherly developed in [Section 2](#).

- increasing the impact of the CE (Citizenship Engagement) strategy (see Section 5)
- engaging them in other activities of the project
- communicate the project outcomes
- and assure the long-term sustainability of the project by demonstrating its current success among service-users.

6.3.3 Target audience

CE and Communication campaigns, even when they appear to address the general public, actually are directed toward specific and particular segments of the population as seen in [FIGURE 27](#). Some campaigns often include more than one target audience and can include both upstream and downstream groups.

Figure 27 - Target groups in-line with the 4 helixes for community engagement

These groups are furtherly explained in section 1 and the segmentation as regards the communication strategy for sustaining the Citizens' Engagement is drafted in section 6.4.. The MatchUp strategy for Valencia includes both types of actions within the campaigns and the overall concept, upstream and downstream as defined in 6.3.4.

6.3.4 Strategy

Our strategy provides the linkage between the how and why components and a roadmap and sense of direction for generating the essential messages while also offering a rationale for the various actions that are proposed. The proposed strategy is based on communication campaigns, as defined below.

As regards the general approach but also the approach taken for implementing specific campaigns and actions, we can distinguish between upstream and downstream perspective.

- Upstream: instead of directly targeting the service-users, sometimes it would be better to reach a group that have interpersonal influence and can create change thanks to its relation with the service-users. In addition, these groups could be more likely to influence and have the ability to modify contextual factors. For instance, policy makers, public administration officers, community leaders or investors are groups to be considered in upstream actions. **However, upstream initiatives might be necessary for downstream efforts to be effective.**
- Downstream: to recruit service-users for the MatchUp project will involve a significant effort in social marketing and public communication. The efforts should be made to design and implement the campaigns responding to the specific needs and preferences of citizens and main sub-targets.

6.3.5 Tactics

Strategies refer to broad roads on the map, and tactics are the small alleys or specific activities that must be undertaken to address the objectives of the campaign. In this case, personal networks of Valencian partners will be used for engaging the community and foster local awareness provides opportunities for unpaid media placement and contact with opinion leaders.

6.3.6 Media

MatchUp's communication campaigns require the use of the aforementioned virtual platforms, mass media, interpersonal channels, small group meetings, and one-on-one discussions, as the case may be. Media of choice will depend on the key message and specific audience of each communication campaign.

6.3.7 Calendar

Each communication campaign should specify a calendar. The calendar must consider the following phases:

- **Launch** phase where the campaign is being initiated. It is common for the launch to involve the greatest media presence.
- The second phase is often the **body** of the campaign. Media are often used incrementally to remind the audience of the message.
- The third phase is usually the **final media push** before the campaign ends

6.3.8 Summary of resources

The **TABLE 6** summarises the resources available for supporting the Citizen Engagement strategy (5.1.) through the aforementioned communication strategy. These resources will be considered for designing the communication campaigns plan, as developed in the section 6.4. Resources are grouped into groups of actions, specifying degrees of participation, targets, tools and channels. The timing estimation is also considered for organising the overall plan for launching communication campaigns.

Table 6. Specification of available resources

Action / group of actions (if applicable)	Action degree of participation (see chapter 4.2)	Targeted public	C&D Tools	C&D Channels	Timing estimation
Necessary citizen participation (9 acciones) especificar cuáles	Involve and Collaborate	-Public authorities -Research Community -Policy Makers -Construction -Media -Investors -Citizens	- Communication campaign (Ref. Communication campaigns)- Short presentation video and interviews -Newsletter -Flyers -Webinars	-Policy learning platforms -Website -Social Media -Press and News Releases -Events and conferences	In order to correctly involve everyone, communication actions must begin at least three months before. To maintain people's attention, it is recommended that the communication campaign continue until the actions end.
Required involvement and recruitment of participants	Involve and Collaborate	- Citizens - Construction - Investors - Media	- Communication campaign (Ref. Communication campaigns)	- Mupis - Buses - Mailings - Press -Neighbourhood associations -Seminars/ workshops -Network "Conecta Energía	Actions Will be planned for starting 1 month before the A2-A5 and finishing 1 month after.
Necessary citizen involvement (12 actions)	Consult	-Research Community -Media -Investors -Citizens	-Short presentation video and interviews -Flyers	-Website -Press release -Social Media	You can start communicating one month before the action starts.
Demonstrative Actions (14 actions)	Inform	-Citizens -Research Community		-Website -Press release -Social Media	Communicating the action a couple of days before is enough.
A.45. Citizens' engagement	Empower	- Citizens - Business - Administration - Research & Education	-Communication campaign (Ref. Communication campaigns)	-Policy learning platforms -Website -Social Media -Newsletter -Press and News Releases -Events	

6.4 Communication campaigns

The timing for executing the communication strategy will be organised in-line with the five communication campaigns specified above (see: Summary of resources).

Communication Campaigns (CC) comprise the overall organisation of the communication strategy and are in-line with the action plan (See Action Plan). These campaigns are ordered by lower to higher degree of use of resources and media effort. The figure below explains the general framework of the communication campaigns plan as well as the interaction with the Action Plan.

Figure 28 - Structure of the communication campaigns plan in-line with the action plan (section 5)

While the **FIGURE 28** explains the overall structure, the **TABLE 7. COMMUNICATION CAMPAIGNS PLAN** summarises the plan and organisation of communication campaigns, including targets, key messages, strategic approach, channels and resources.

Table 7. Communication campaigns plan

ID	Aim	Target group	Key Message	Approach	Channels	Resources
INFORM						
CC1.1.	To inform all stakeholders about the MatchUp Project	Society as a whole	<i>MatchUp proposes innovations in the fields of ICT, energy, sustainable entrepreneurship, mobility and transport and participation for all.</i>	Downstream	Local press/TV/Radio Social Media Virtual platform and local Website	Current media presence. Flyers Posters Personal networks and relations with media
CC1.2.	To disseminate the MatchUp concept and aims		<i>That's how MatchUp works We'll keep you up-to-date!</i>	Downstream	Website Social Media Local press, TV or radio	Current media presence.
CONSULT						
CC2.1	To obtain valuable and information feedback.	Citizens, service users	<i>Without you, MatchUp does not make sense. Let us know your opinion!</i>	Downstream	Virtual platform and local Website Social Media Local press, TV or radio	Current media presence. New tools for feedback gathering (ref. 5.2. Citizen Engagement activities)
CC2.2.		Research community	<i>MatchUp provides transferable information on how feedback could be obtained and analysed during the implementation of a large pilot project</i>	Upstream	Personal relations with universities and departments. Events and conferences	Current media presence.
INVOLVE						
CC3.1	To recruit citizens for participating in the pilot phase, expecting a high degree of involvement and collaboration .	Citizens Service-users	<i>Your participation led to economic development and prosperity for your neighbourhood and community. Participate in our events [substitute by the name of the event in each case] Join our online forum!</i>	Downstream	Events Local press/TV/Radio Social Media Virtual platform and local Website	Current media presence. Flyers Webinars Presentations Personal networks and relations with media
CC3.2.		Public authorities Policy makers	<i>Sustainable entrepreneurship is a key for success. Participate in our events [substitute by the name of the event in each case] Join our online forum!</i>	Upstream	Virtual platform and local Website	media

CC3.3		Building Investors	<i>CE implies a higher value of products and business through validation and acceptance testing. Join our online forum!</i>		Virtual platform and local Website Social Media Newsletter Press and News Releases Events	
CC.3.4		Research community	<i>Community-engaged projects could contribute to fill the gap in implementation research. Join our online forum!</i>		conferences	
COLLABORATE						
CC4	To involve citizens in the decision-making process through the collaboration and consultation with the public in all relevant areas	Citizens Business Administration Research & Education	<i>We need your participation in the decision-making. We want to hear your voice: Join now the decision making process!</i> Strengthening collaboration for involving you in the decision-making process!	Downstream	Events Local press/TV/Radio Social Media Virtual platform and local Website	Current media presence. Flyers Webinars Presentations Personal networks and relations with media
EMPOWER						
CC5	To raise loyalty and engagement during the pilot implementation	Service-users (i.e., people participating and already involved)	<i>Through MatchUP, we implement what you decide. Digital democracy: what is it? MatchUp project is focused on your needs. We focus on you.</i>	Downstream	Website Social Media Local press, TV or radio Virtual platform and local Website	Current media presence. Flyers Webinars Presentations Personal networks and relations with media

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Annex I. Other relevant actors and services in the district

Public services

- SPORTS

Poliesportiu Cabanyal
Poliesportiu Beteró
Poliesportiu Dr. Lluch
Poliesportiu Nazaret

- MARKETS

Mercado Municipal del Cabanyal
Mercado Municipal del Grao
Mercado Municipal de Nazaret

- HEALTH

Centro de Salud Serrería I
Centro de Salud Vicente Brull
Centro de Salud de Nazaret
Centro de Especialidades del Grao

- CULTURAL

Biblioteca Casa de La Reina
Biblioteca Constantí Llombart
Teatre El Musical

- HEALTHCARE / SOCIAL

Centro Especializado de Atención a los Mayores
Centre Salut Mental de la Malvarrosa
Centro Ocupacional Isabel de Villena
Centro de Día de Jóvenes Malvarrosa
Centro de día de menores San Vicente Paúl en Nazaret

- OTHERS

Observatori Canvi Climàtic

Citizens and civil society organizations

- YOUTH ASSOCIATIONS

Asociación Infantil y Juvenil Nou Grup
Juniors Parroquia del Rosario
Juniors Parroquia Sta M^a Del Mar

- MUSICAL SOCIETIES

Sociedad Musical Unión de Pescadores
Sociedad Musical Poblados Marítimos
Ateneo Musical del Puerto
Coral Parroquial Virgen del Rosario del Canyamellar

- SEAFERING HOLY WEEK

Junta Mayor De La Semana Santa Marinera
Corporación de Sayones

Hermandad del Sant Cáliz de la Cena
 Santa Hermandad de la Muerte y Resurrección del Señor
 Hermandad del Stísimo Cristo del Salvador Y del Amparo
 Hermandad de María Santísima de las Angustias
 Cofradía de la Oración de Jesús en el Huerto
 Real Cofradía de Jesús en la Columna
 Germandat de la Coronació d'espines del Nostre Senyor Jesucrist
 Germandat del Santíssim Ecce-Homo
 Real Hermandad de Jesús con la Cruz y Cristo Resucitado
 Corporación de Longinos
 Hermandad del Stísimo Cristo del Perdón
 Hermandad del Stísimo Cristo del Salvador
 Corporació Granaders de la Verge
 Hermandad del Santo Silencio y Vera Cruz
 Corporación de Petrorianos Y Penitentes
 Hermandad del Santo Encuentro
 Real Hermandad de la Santa Faz
 Hermandad de la Crucifixión del Señor
 Hermandad del Stísimo Cristo de los Afligidos
 Hermandad de Vestas del Santísimo Cristo del Buen Acierto
 Cofradía de Granaderos de la Virgen de la Soledad
 Hermandad Descendimiento del Señor
 Hermandad del Santo Sepulcro
 Real Hermandad de la Flagelación del Señor
 Hermandad de Jesús De Medinaceli
 Real Hermandad de Nuestro Padre Jesús Nazareno
 Pontificia y Real Hermandad del Santísimo Cristo de la Concordia
 Hermandad Stísimo Cristo de la Palma
 Cofradía de Granaderos de la Virgen de los Dolores

- FALLAS (Municipal festivity)

Rosario - Plaza Calabuig
 Arquitecto Alfaro - Francisco Cubells
 La Cruz, Plaza - Los Angeles
 Blocs Platja
 Jose Benlliure - Teatro de La Marina
 Barraca - Trav. Iglesia Rosario
 Justo Vilar - Plaza Mercado Cabañal
 Progreso - Teatro de la Marina
 Barraca - Columbretes
 Ramon de Rocafull - Conde Alaquàs
 Vidal De Canelles - Sanchez Coello
 Jose Benlliure - Vicente Guillot
 Escalante - Marina
 Reina - Vicente Guillot
 Barraca - Espadán
 Escalante - Amparo Guillen
 Padre Luis Navarro - Remonta
 San Pedro - Virgen de Vallivana

- POLITICAL PARTIES

EUPV
 PODEMOS Círculo Marítimo

COMPROMÍS Marítim
PSPV Marítim
CIUDADANOS València
PP.CV Marítim

- RELIGIOUS

Parroquia Cristo Redentor - S. Rafael Arcángel
Parroquia Nuestra Señora de los Ángeles
Parroquia Sta. María Del Mar
Parroquia Ntra. Señora Del Rosario
Iglesia Evangélica Rey de Reyes
Iglesia Evangélica El Salvador
Iglesia Evangélica "Rúgul Aprins"

- SPORTS

Club Atletisme Poblats Marítims
Ca Running Poblats Marítims
A.D. Sociedad Deportiva Poblats Maritims
U.D. Marítimo Cabañal
Club Futbol Cabanyal Canyamelar
Club Muntanysme Maritim
Asociación Valenciana de Fútbol de Botones
Club de Hándbol Canyamelar-Marítim
Fòrum de l'Esport

- OTHERS

Cofradía de Pescadores

